

Showcase to Illustrate How the Web-Server iKcr-PseEns is Working

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In 2018 a very powerful web-server predictor has been established for predicting lysine crotonylation sites in histone proteins [1].

To see how the web-server is working, please do the following.

Step 1. Opening the web-server at <http://www.jci-bioinfo.cn/iKcr-PseEns>, you will see the top page of **iKcr-PseEns** on your computer screen, as shown in **Fig.1**. Click on the [Read Me](#) button to see a brief introduction about the predictor.

Figure 1. A semi-screenshot for the top page of the web server **iKcr-PseEns** at <http://www.jci-bioinfo.cn/iKcr-PseEns>

Step 2. Either type or copy/paste your query protein sequences into the input box at the center of **Fig.1**. The input sequence should be in the FASTA format. For the examples of sequences in FASTA format, click the [Example](#) button right above the input box.

Step 3. Click the [Submit](#) button to get the predicted result. For example, if you use the [Example](#) window as the input, the corresponding predicted results are quite consistent with experimental observations.

Step 4. As shown on the lower panel of **Fig.1**, you may also choose the batch prediction by entering your e-mail address and your desired batch input file (in FASTA format of course) via the [Browse](#) button. To see the sample of batch input file, click on the button [Batch-example](#).

Step 5. Click the [Supporting Information](#) button to download the benchmark dataset used in this study.

Step 6. Click the [Citation](#) button to find the relevant papers that document the detailed development and algorithm of **iKcr-PseEns**

It is anticipated that the Web-Server will be very useful because the vast majority of biological scientists can easily get their desired results without the need to go through the complicated equations in [1] that were presented just for the integrity in developing the predictor.

Also, note that the web-server predictor has been developed by strictly observing the guidelines of “Chou’s 5-steps rule” and hence have the following notable merits (see, e.g., [2-29] and three comprehensive review papers [30-32]): (1) crystal clear in logic development, (2) completely transparent in operation, (3) easily to repeat the reported results by other investigators, (4) with high potential in stimulating other sequence-analyzing methods, and (5) very convenient to be used by the majority of experimental scientists.

It has not escaped our notice that during the development of iRNA-2methyl web-server, the approach of general pseudo amino acid components [33] or PseAAC [34] had been utilized and hence its accuracy would be much higher than its counterparts, as concurred by many investigators [33-73][2-6, 8-11, 13, 18, 26, 30, 32, 74-301]

For the wonderful and awesome roles of the “5-steps rule” in driving proteome, genome analyses and drug development, see a series of recent papers [31, 32, 292, 302-311] where the rule and its wide applications have been very impressively presented from various aspects or at different angles.

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